

Enhanced Genomics Virtual Lab

All Australian bioscience researchers now have the opportunity to more easily access and apply bioinformatics approaches to their research, without needing to worry about resourcing, deploying, configuring and performing other system administration tasks that previously precluded the use of cloud and high performance compute resources.

This project provides a "data enhanced" and "user-enhanced" managed Genomics Virtual Laboratory (GVL) service for all researchers in Australia, with a strong focus on the Graphical User Interface (GUI) workflow and tool repository platform – Galaxy Australia (<https://usegalaxy.org.au>) and trains the community in the use of this platform.

Start date

13 March 2018

Expected completion date

31 December 2019

Investment by ARDC

\$625,000

Co-investment partners

- [BioPlatforms Australia \(BPA\)](#)
- [Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation and QFAB Bioinformatics](#)
- [Melbourne Bioinformatics](#)
- [The Australian National University \(ANU\)](#)
- [University of New South Wales \(UNSW\)](#)
- [University of Western Australia \(UWA\)](#)
- [Monash University](#)
- [The University of Melbourne](#)
- [University of Tasmania \(UTAS\)](#)
- [The University of Adelaide](#)
- [Southern Cross University \(SCU\)](#)
- [James Cook University \(JCU\)](#)
- [EMBL-Australia Bioinformatics Resource \(EMBL-ABR\)](#)
- [University of Queensland Research Computing Centre \(RCC\)](#)
- [Metabolomics Australia](#)
- [Australian Genomics Research facility \(AGRF\)](#)
- [Australian Bioinformatics and Computational Biology Society \(ABACBS\)](#)

Lead node

2. Upgrading and updating Galaxy and GVL - November 2018

Align the analysis components of the managed GVL service (especially Galaxy Australia) and incorporate functionalities established by the global development community to ensure the Australian service remains current.

4. Training

The development of a 'train-the-trainer' program. Realign all training materials (previously and newly created) to the new service, and make it available from a single location. Deliver courses in person and via webinar. Four national webinars held, reaching over ten national sites and 400 registrants.

1. Creation of Galaxy Australia

Consolidation of hardware and resources from Galaxy-Melbourne and Galaxy-Queensland into Galaxy Australia, providing a national Galaxy service. Repurposing of Galaxy-Melbourne resources and addition of NCI resources to underpin Galaxy training events and computational intensive analyses respectively.

3. Metadata addition - Sep 2018

Establish a process to ensure metadata is added when 'on boarding' new reference datasets. Improve metadata for all existing reference datasets. Coordination with global reference data repository to strengthen global reference metadata.

Core features

National training network

Existing materials have been consolidated, and new training resources developed.

National Galaxy Australia service

All Australian researchers now have access to sophisticated biomolecular data analysis capability on top of cloud compute resources; with reliable, quality controlled and trusted analysis tools and relevant training and support.

Who is this project for?

Galaxy Australia is open to all members of the research community. This includes researchers, students, government research bodies and international collaborators. The service was historically focused on genomics and supports over 850 analytical tools with over 200 genomes that can be referenced with these tools. However as a workflow platform agnostic to data type Galaxy Australia is developing metabolomics analytical processing options.

What does this project enable?

All Australian bioscience researchers now have access to a professionally managed and appropriately resourced on-line computational service platform to underpin their biomolecular data analyses. This national managed service allows collaborative and borderless research for researchers across all Australian States and territories, and by invitation, their international collaborators. The alignment to the *usegalaxy* global efforts means that Galaxy Australia has access to the most up-to-date and best practice analytical options in the increasingly diverse field of genomics and metabolomics.

Handy resources

Use [Galaxy Australia](#)

Access [training materials](#)

Explore the [Galaxy Australia community](#)

Follow [Galaxy Australia](#) at Twitter [@GalaxyAustralia](#)

Use the [Genomics Virtual Laboratory \(GVL\)](#)

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